

A Quantum Free Particle Does Not Seem to Maximize Spatial Entropy

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A free particle spends the same dt in each fixed dx (for one dimensional motion). This leads to the notion of $P(x)dx=dx/L$, where L is some arbitrary length. The point we wish to make is that there is maximum entropy in L because one has no idea where the particle is. It has equal probability to be at any x in L . The quantum free particle wavefunction, $\exp(ipx)$, however, has bias in x as seen in $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ and so does not represent maximum entropy in space. One may argue that $\exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L} = 1/L$, but a quantum particle interferes with two slits separated by about a wavelength, \hbar/p and so the bias in space, namely the discernment of the wavelength, means non-maximum entropy. As a result, a quantum particle has an uncertain or probabilistic x position within a wavelength, but the probability form $\exp(ipx)$ represents a specific structure in space. We argue that this is why one has a distinct crest-trough pattern from 2-slit interference instead of equal probability for all angles which would maximize entropy.

Mathematically, one may maximize Shannon's entropy $-P_1(x) \ln(P_1(x))$ subject to the constraint $\int P_1(x) dx = 1$, where b is Lagrange multiplier and i introduces periodicity, but we argue that the presence of x in the constraint already indicates x dependence of $P_1(x)$ suggesting that one cannot have maximum entropy which is given by no x dependent constraint, i.e. $P(x)dx=dx/L$. Thus, the presence of momentum p and energy E for a free particle creates probability in space and time, but in such a way that one does not have maximum entropy. In other words, p and E give structure to space and time. Higher p gives higher resolution or structure to space and higher E , higher structure to time.

Classical Physics and Maximum Entropy

A classical particle is represented by $x(t)$ which means that one may discern every point in space and time, but at the same time is linked with maximum entropy in space through:

$$P(x)dx = dx/L \text{ for a particle with constant } p \quad ((1))$$

Here L is an arbitrary length and one has a uniform distribution because the free particle spends the same dt in each dx . Another way to state this is to say that there is no bias in space because each x point may be resolved.

Quantum Free Particle

We have argued in previous notes that L is an arbitrary length and that a quantum particle should have a built-in noarbitrary physical length.. We suggested that $c= E/p$ for all frames for a photon suggests:

$$\text{Space unit} = \text{constant}/p \text{ and } \text{time unit} = \text{constant}/ E \quad ((2)) \text{ where constant} = \hbar$$

This in turn leads to $\exp(ipx)$ for a spatial probability such that: $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}\exp(-ipx)/\sqrt{L} = 1/L$.

We argue, however, that despite this fact, $\exp(ipx)$ represents a fixed length in space, \hbar/p , in which there is x uncertainty. This length is repeated and so in order to be distinguished one cannot have a uniform probability distribution in x over \hbar/p . This means that certain x points are associated with different probabilities than others even in the complex case $\exp(ipx)$. To see experimentally that this is the case, one may consider 2-slit interference which only occurs if the two slits are about one wavelength apart. Thus, the presence of a wavelength not only means limited resolution, up to \hbar/p , but also non-maximum entropy in space. In other words, by giving space structure through \hbar/p (a ruler gradation), one is removing entropy. The higher p , the more structure space has. As a result, the crest-trough pattern in $\cos(px)$ and $\sin(px)$ represents order or structure and reduced entropy.

If one considers the 2-slit experiment, it may seem that disorder is created, but the crest pattern represents structure, i.e. some specific order in space. If a photon or particle heading to a 2-slit apparatus could be pulled in probabilistically by one slit or the other, but then maximum entropy imposed, one would have each angle from the center of the slits to a screen representing the same probability for a photon/particle and there would be no light and dark patterns. Thus, the two-slit result represents order above maximum entropy.

Maximization of Entropy Subject to a Constraint

Traditionally, one maximizes Shannon's entropy $-P_1(x)\ln(P_1(x))$ subject to a constraint. If one introduces an x average as a constraint, this means that $x P_1(x)$ appears and $P_1(x)$ must depend on x and cannot be the classical $P(x)dx=dx/L$. Thus, even though L is a fixed length and there is an average x in this length (the center point), L and its position are completely arbitrary. The maximization of entropy subject to an average x suggests some probability structure which actually creates x average. In the case of \hbar/p defining the normalization length, there must be a probability structure which defines it. Thus:

$$\text{Maximize: } -P_1(x)\ln(P_1(x)) + i b x P_1(x) \quad ((1))$$

The fact that one has a known x ave means that there is a known length in the problem. The "i" represents periodicity so there is an x average for repeated units of this value. This seems to suggest a probability structure which defines the length and so $P_1(x)$ cannot be uniform. Mathematically this follows because x is present in ((1)). Thus, one does not have maximum entropy in x , but rather a structure based on the length given by \hbar/p . In other words, the x uncertainty region introduces a lack of resolution, but at the same structure to space, i.e. reduces the entropy of $P(x)=\text{constant}$.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that that the quantum $\exp(ipx)$ introduces structure into space because even though there is a limit of resolution given by \hbar/p , there is a probability distribution

$(\cos(px) \text{ and } \sin(x))$ which defines this length by being nonuniform, unlike the classical $P(x)dx=dx/L$. This means that there is less entropy than for a uniform distribution, i.e. structure. The higher p , the more structure or order present. As a result, a 2-slit interference pattern instead of demonstrating disorder, has peaks and troughs which define an order in space linked with the order associated with \hbar/p .